

STRETCHING the PHARMA: ANTI-COMPETITIVE POTENTIAL COMPLYING WITH the COMPETITION LAW?

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Abstract- The quest for attaining the pinnacle of the pharma industry competence has gained momentum over the last few years and the synergetic amalgamations to cement their foundations on the corporate front are an absolute testament. Corporate Restructuring paves the way as a last survival for some and strategic edge for many enterprises. The pharmaceutical industries fostered by regulatory changes and policy-induced flexibilities are being reshaped through a number of Mergers as well as Acquisitions resulting in consolidation of the industry. Striking the opportunities available for their economic growth, the Domestic firms have taken the route of mergers to restructure their business whereas, the foreign firms targeted their entry into specific markets through acquisitions and have raised their monopoly. In this very context, the article attempts to examine the impact of Mergers and Acquisitions on the pharmaceutical market structure in major industries of the manufacturing sector. Merger clauses though very generic and standardised in nature, can result in many unwelcoming surprises, the hidden opportunist intent and magnitude must be looked at through, with a comprehensive approach. The role of regulators plays a vital role, to step back, zoom in the details, anti-competitive intent and practices from a birds-eye view. The article examines the spectacle, that sectors are able to extract more profits through restructuring techniques, in the view of which practices including predatory pricing and abuse of dominance.

Keywords- Competition Law, Pharmaceuticals, pharmacy, anti-competitive practises, patent abuse, evergreening, price fixing, collusions, mergers, biology.

I. INTRODUCTION

Competition refers to the state of the market when sellers engage in distinct efforts to attract buyers and fulfil their business objectives. The combination of competition and liberalisation serves to unleash the entrepreneurial forces inside the economy. Competition provides customers with a diverse range of options at affordable costs, fosters innovation and productivity, and facilitates the efficient deployment of resources.

The New Economic Policy of 1991, which encompassed the principles of Liberalisation, Privatisation, and Globalisation, significantly expanded the scope for market forces and reduced the role of the Government

in business and several other economic sectors. The need for new competition law arose due to the recognition that the existing Monopolies and Restrictive Trade Practises Act, 1969 (MRTP Act) had become outdated in certain aspects. Consequently, there was a shift in focus from merely regulating monopolies to actively promoting competition within the Indian market. In 1999, a definitive committee was appointed with the purpose of proposing enhanced competition legislation that aligns with global advancements to effectively address the specific circumstances of India. The panel proposed the implementation of new legislation on competition, referred to as the Competition Act, as well as the establishment of a competition regulatory body, known as the Competition Commission of India. Additionally, the panel recommended the repeal of the MRTP Act and the dissolution of the MRTP Commission.¹

The establishment of the Competition Commission of India (Commission) falls under the purview of the Competition Act, 2002 (the Act). Its primary objectives are to prevent practices that have a negative impact on competition, foster and maintain competition in Indian markets, safeguard consumer interests, and uphold the freedom of trade conducted by other market participants in India.²

The primary objective of the Competition Act is to govern and oversee two distinct categories of agreements:

1. agreements that are deemed anti-competitive and include collusion among rivals (referred to as horizontal agreements),
2. agreements that are anti-competitive and involve firms or individuals operating at various stages or levels within the production chain (referred to as vertical agreements).

According to the provisions of the Competition Act, several types of horizontal agreements are deemed to result in an Appreciable Adverse Effect on Competition within the jurisdiction of India. The assumption does not imply that all purported horizontal agreements are inherently anti-competitive. It allows the parties involved in such an agreement to present information demonstrating that their agreement does not lead to an appreciable adverse effect on competition (and to challenge the presumption. However, this presumption does not extend to vertical agreements. Vertical agreements are generally deemed permissible unless it can be demonstrated that they result in, or are expected to result in, an appreciable adverse effect on competition within the jurisdiction of India. The Competition Act in India encompasses a comprehensive enumeration of horizontal agreements that are considered to result in an Appreciable

¹ Competition Law and Indian Pharmaceutical Industry, Centre for Trade and Development (Centad), New Delhi 2010 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS, <https://www.cci.gov.in/public/images/marketstudie/en/docs1652437987.pdf>.

² Priyamvada Singh, Pharmaceutical Sector and the Indian Competition Law: Probable Paradigm Shift? (Sept 27, 2023, 01:12 PM), <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4230608>.

Adverse Effect on Competition.³ Additionally, it includes an extensive list of vertical agreements that may be subject to prohibition based on their impact on competitive circumstances inside India.

II. APPLICABILITY OF COMPETITION LAWS IN PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR

The drug market in India plays a pivotal role in fostering economic growth inside the country. Based on sales figures, it can be observed that the Indian pharmaceutical industry ranks as the fourth biggest globally. In 2010, the Competition Commission of India issued a study that had been commissioned by the Centre for Trade and Development. The objective of this study was to investigate the concerns pertaining to the Indian pharmaceutical industry, encompassing both the horizontal perspective (involving firms operating at the same market level) and the vertical perspective (encompassing rivals at various stages of production). The analysis unveiled a multitude of inequitable practices inside the sector. According to their claims, there exists evidence suggesting an inefficient allocation of resources in the distribution of pharmaceutical products.

Available studies indicate that the profitability margins within the distribution chain are notably high, particularly in the case of non-DPCO drugs and non-scheduled drugs within the pharmaceutical industry in India. These circumstances have significant ramifications for rivalry within the industry and the inequitable accumulation of wealth through the transfer of resources.

The Competition Commission of India functions as an independent regulatory body overseeing off-market activities. This implies that it does not exert influence or disrupt operations inside a certain industry or domain. The intervention occurs solely after the occurrence of a market disruption. The Competition Commission of India (CCI) has levied over one hundred sanctions, with a significant majority falling under Section 3, which pertains to addressing anti-competitive agreements and cartels.

The pharmaceutical sector has been the target of persistent criticism. The importance of this issue is in the meticulous oversight of anti-competitive practises and merger strategies, which is essential for maintaining the effective operation of the healthcare system, while simultaneously achieving a harmonious equilibrium between cost-effectiveness, advancement, and availability. However, instances have been documented whereby apprehensions have been raised over the quality of pharmaceuticals supplied to India by global pharmaceutical businesses. There have been several media reports alleging that the pharmaceutical items produced in India do not meet the required standards of quality. There is a substantial amount of anecdotal and factual data available regarding this topic, which justifies the need for an investigation to be conducted by the appropriate authorities.

³ Bharat Budholia & Atish Ghosal, Pharmaceutical Antitrust 2021, AZB (Sept. 25, 2023, 2:35 PM), <https://www.azbpartners.com/bank/pharmaceutical-antitrust-2021-india/>.

III. OBJECTIVES AND PRINCIPLES OF COMPETITION LAWS IN PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR IN INDIA

The principal aim of competition legislation is to foster competition within the pharmaceutical sector. A competitive market fosters an environment that incentivizes enterprises to engage in innovation, price reduction, and enhancement of product quality.

Additionally, it safeguards the welfare of customers. Competition legislation endeavours to guarantee that customers are provided with a diverse range of reasonably priced pharmaceuticals and healthcare alternatives. Competition within the pharmaceutical industry serves as a catalyst for innovation, since it incentivizes businesses to engage in the development of novel medications and technology. The purpose of this measure is to prevent corporations from participating in anti-competitive behaviours that impede the progress of innovation. The primary objective of competition legislation is to improve the operational effectiveness of the pharmaceutical market by promoting the best allocation of resources and eliminating any artificial obstacles that may impede the entry or exit of enterprises.⁴

Competition legislation effectively restricts the formation of anti-competitive agreements among pharmaceutical corporations. These encompass anti-competitive pharmaceutical activities such as price-fixing, market allocation, and other collusive practises that serve to restrict competition. Companies that possess a prevailing market position bear a distinct obligation to refrain from exploiting their authority. Competition law serves as a regulatory framework that prohibits pharmaceutical companies from partaking in activities that have the potential to undermine competition, such as participating in predatory pricing, refusing to engage in business dealings, or establishing tying arrangements. Regulatory bodies conduct thorough examinations of mergers and acquisitions within the pharmaceutical sector with the objective of preventing any significant reduction in competition.

Regulatory authorities have the authority to enforce requirements or impede transactions that constitute a risk to market competition. Patents have a crucial role in stimulating innovation; yet, in cases when pharmaceutical corporations exploit their patents to establish anti-competitive obstacles, competition law may intervene. For instance, by the extension of patents beyond a justifiable duration or through the adoption of "evergreening" strategies aimed at impeding the entry of generic competitors. The promotion of competition necessitates the presence of transparency in pricing and discounts.

Pharmaceutical businesses may be obligated by regulatory measures to provide price information and ensure equitable access to discounts and rebates. Competition legislation promotes the prompt introduction

⁴ Natasha Nayak, Competition Impediments in The Pharmaceutical Sector in India Work in Progress, (Sept. 21, 2023, 11:55 AM), https://iica.nic.in/images/sclmr_research/Pharmaceuticals%20Sector.pdf.

of generic pharmaceuticals into the market subsequent to the termination of patent exclusivity. It serves as a deterrent to activities that impede or obstruct the progress of generic competition, such as the use of pay-for-delay agreements. Competition law include provisions that safeguard the welfare of customers by prohibiting pharmaceutical corporations from engaging in deceptive marketing practises or disseminating misleading advertising.⁵ Competition law in the global pharmaceutical business can have far-reaching international consequences. Government entities collaborate and coordinate attempts to tackle transnational anti-competitive behaviour. Competition law acknowledges the significance of safeguarding public health. In some instances, there may be provisions or allowances made to safeguard the availability of vital pharmaceuticals.

IV. ANTICOMPETITIVE PRACTICES IN PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR

Pharmaceutical industry is a highly regulated sector that has led to reduced competition in the market. Anti-competitive activities are resorted to when there is absence of fair competition which deprives customers and small producers of the benefits of competitive markets. The Indian pharma diaspora is in constant metamorphosis as both Indian and foreign companies are perennially engaged in stretching this sector through global deal making. Indian pharmaceutical area substances over 50% of global demand for diverse vaccines, 40% of commonplace demand within the US and 25% of all medication inside the UK. Globally, India ranks third in terms of pharmaceutical manufacturing by way of volume and 14th through cost. The domestic pharmaceutical industry includes a network of 3,000 drug corporations and 10,500 production units.⁶

The competition control regimes generally seek to provide a framework to regulate the pharmaceutical sector, yet the growing bullish nature of the contemporary market, signals the rising anti-competitive practices. The term ‘appreciable adverse effect on competition’ is not defined specifically, though S.21(4) of the 2002 act provides an illustrative and non-exhaustive list of factors to be considered by Competition Authority while verifying the validity of the deal.⁷

⁵ Margaret K. Kyle, “COMPETITION LAW, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY, AND THE PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR.” *Antitrust Law Journal*, vol. 81, 1–36 (2016).

⁶Natasha Nayak, *Competition Impediments in The Pharmaceutical Sector in India Work in Progress*, (Sept. 25, 2023, 10:04 AM), https://iica.nic.in/images/sclmr_research/Pharmaceuticals%20Sector.pdf.

⁷ Rishi Shroff & Ashwita Ambast, Ss. 5 and 6 of the Competition Act, 2002: Demystifying the Competition Implications of Mergers and Acquisitions in India, 20 *J. FIN. CRIME* 88 (2013).

V. EXAMINING PRICE FIXING AND COLLUSION

In the history of antitrust enforcement, patents have occupied centre stage in a number of Supreme Court cases addressing horizontal price fixing and conspiracies to monopolize.⁸ As one eminent economist has observed, "some of the worst price fixing schemes in American history were erected on a foundation of agreements to cross-license complementary and competing patents."⁹ Distortions created by collusion and corruption in these markets increase the cost and reduce the quality and quantity of these essential services and infrastructure; impose penalties on those who rely on them, especially the less advantaged; and diminish growth and create public safety risks.¹⁰ In a classic price-fixing conspiracy, firms directly agree to raise or maintain prices for competing products and establish mechanisms by which to detect and punish defectors. In concentrated industries, however, such overt communication is often unnecessary. Rather, through a combination of announcements, investments, and algorithms, companies in concentrated industries can raise or maintain their prices without ever explicitly agreeing with one another to do so. This "tacit collusion," more innocuously described as "conscious parallelism," is a driving force behind firms' increased prices in oligopolies.¹¹

VI. UNPACKING PATENT ABUSE AND EVERGREENING

In part, these prices arise due to the inelastic demand for lifesaving drugs and the patents that create short-term legal monopolies. The economic rationale for patent protection flows from the fact that the investment made by inventors necessarily precedes any financial benefits received from the discovery of new products or more efficient production processes. Patent law prevents copiers from free riding so that innovators can reap the reward of monopoly profits for their innovation. Thus, there is a trade-off between innovation and affordability.¹² Evergreening is a strategy by which patent owners extend the life of a patent monopoly, surrounding an original inventive patent with numerous additional patents for modifications or variations to the original invention (secondary patents). The sub-set of secondary patents owned by the originator company are known as 'evergreening patents', that is, patents designed to further delay generic entry to the market. Only a small number of evergreening patents achieve this effect.¹³

⁸ Notable examples include *United States v. Singer Manufacturing Co.*, 374 U.S. 174 (1963); *United States v. New Wrinkle, Inc.*, 342 U.S. 371 (1952); *United States v. Gypsum Co.*, 333 U.S. 364 (1948); *United States v. Line Material Co.*, 333 U.S. 287 (1948); *Hartford-Empire Co. v. United States*, 324 U.S. 570 (1945); *Standard Oil Co. (Indiana) v. United States*, 283 U.S. 163 (1931).

⁹ F.M. Scherer & David Ross, *Industrial Market Structure and Economic Performance* (1990, Ssrn.com (2023), <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1496716>).

¹⁰ Robert D. Anderson, Alison Jones & William E. Kovacic, *Preventing Corruption, Supplier Collusion, and the Corrosion of Civic Trust: A Procompetitive Program to Improve the Effectiveness and Legitimacy of Public Procurement*, 26 *GEO. MASON L. REV.* 1233 (2019).

¹¹ Brendan Ballou, *The "No Collusion" Rule*, 32 *Stan. L. & Pol'y Rev.* 213 (2021).

¹² Roger D. Blair, Christine Piette Durrance & Tirza J. Angerhofer, *Patents and Monopoly Pricing of Pharmaceuticals, in Antitrust Policy in Health Care Markets*, 37–73 (2022).

¹³ Hazel V. J. Moir, *Pharmaceutical Patents and Evergreening*, in *The Cambridge Handbook of Investment-Driven Intellectual Property* 133–152 (Enrico Bonadio & Patrick Goold eds., 2023).

VII. ANALYSING STRATEGIES FOR MARKET EXCLUSIVITY

The pharmaceutical industry is under increasing pressure on many fronts, from investors requiring larger returns to consumer groups and health authorities demanding cheaper and safer drugs. It is also feeling additional pressure from the infringement upon its profit margins by generic drug producers.¹⁴ Many companies are aggressively pursuing outsourcing contracts in an attempt to counter many of the financial pressures and streamline their operations. Generically, the pharmaceutical industry can easily be considered as a system or a network because innovative activities involve, directly or indirectly, a large variety of actors, including: (different types of) firms; other research organizations, such as universities and other research centres; financial institutions; regulatory authorities; and consumers.¹⁵

VIII. ENFORCEMENT CHALLENGES AND REGULATORY OVERSIGHT IN INDIA

A. The Role of the Competition Commission of India (CCI)

Competition Act, 2002 was enacted to introduce measures for easing the competitive environment. The Act mostly tries to govern three areas of competition which are anticompetitive agreements, abuse of dominance and, combinations among corporate ventures.¹⁶ The Competition Commission of India is a quasi-judicial body established under the Competition Act. It is formed for advocating competition and preventing practices that could have an appreciable adverse effect on the competition of India, and also ensures the freedom of trade, protect the interest of the consumers. Competition Commission of India has dealt with various cases involving anticompetitive practises carried out in the distribution chain of the pharmaceutical sector and has found a violation of Section 3(3) and Section 3(4) of the Act by the trade associations of the chemists and druggists. The primary allegations in these cases generally related to the requirement of compulsory NOC from the trade association for appointing stockist, only members of the associations can be appointed as stockist or distributor, the limit of a number of the wholesaler in an area by the association, mandatory payment to the association in the name of Product Information Service (PIS), fixation of trade margins for stockists, fixation of discount, restrictions on bidding, a boycott of manufacturers, etc.

B. Jurisdictional Challenges in a Global Context

The Competition Commission of India has been vested with broad powers under section 18 that provides power to the commission to "eliminate practices having an adverse effect on competition, promote and

¹⁴ Ian R. Baxendale et al., *Pharmaceutical Strategy and Innovation: An Academics Perspective*, 2 *ChemMedChem* 768 (2007).

¹⁵ Maureen McKelvey, Luigi Orsenigo & Fabio Pammolli, *Pharmaceuticals analysed through the lens of a sectoral innovation system*, in *Sectoral Systems of Innovation: Concepts, Issues and Analyses of Six Major Sectors in Europe* 73–120 (Franco Malerba ed., 2004).

¹⁶ Sanchary Basu, *CCI And Telecom Sectoral Regulator: A Study of Relevance*, 4 (2) *IJLMH* Page 2251 - 2264 (2021).

sustain competition, protect the interests of consumers and ensure freedom of trade carried on by other participants, in markets in India".¹⁷ In contrast decree of competition law, also tries to restrict the negative effects of business power that could affect consumer welfare. Thus there is an overlapping of jurisdiction and powers on the aspect to regulate the exercise of market powers to prevent market failures.

Article 32 of the Act enables CCI to make an enquiry as well as pass certain orders, as such against the enterprises that are established beyond Indian Territory but cause an appreciable adverse effect in India.¹⁸ With the object of performing such role of oversight, these governmental agencies or regulators, which are themselves creatures of legislative acts/ statutes, are empowered to create rules and regulations that have the force of law. In effect, such agencies/regulators are endowed with the ability to make minor policy decisions owing to the dynamic nature of the industries and/or areas which they regulate, as well as due to their advanced knowledge and expertise in how best to deal with issues that may arise. In some cases, the CCI has even invited submissions from the adversarial parties, even though there is no statutory requirement to entertain the same.¹⁹ Thus, It can be said that CCI while exercising its extra territorial jurisdiction, it has informally created a substantive route of inquiry, where it goes beyond merely reviewing the information received but also decides on which course the investigation should take, which is at times in contravention and in conflict with International Jurisdictions.

Similarly, regulators are also often equipped with the ability to initiate inquiries into potential conduct that may be illegal in nature. Such power to initiate inquiries or investigation on its own is referred to as suo moto powers of a regulator, and not all regulators are vested with the same. The existence of suo moto powers may be specific to the nature of activity which a regulator oversees. Further, the scope of a regulator's authority in exercising these powers varies from jurisdiction to jurisdiction.

C. Challenges in Proving Anti-Competitive Behaviour

Competition law evaluates a company by considering it as a 'black box',²⁰ because the antitrust agencies while evaluating the anti-competitive effects, do not consider the internal mechanisms within a firm.²¹ For example for assessing abuse of dominance, antitrust legislations focus on the economic analysis of the

¹⁷ Competition Act, 2002, No. 12, Acts of Parliament, 2003 (India).

¹⁸ Competition Act, 2002, No. 12, Acts of Parliament, 2003 (India).

¹⁹ Indranath Gupta, Vishwas H Devaiah & Dipesh Jain, CCI's Investigation of Abuse of Dominance: Adjudicatory Traits in Prima Facie Opinion, Springer eBooks 185 (2017), (Sept. 28, 2023, 10:15 AM) https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-10-6011-3_9.

²⁰ Florence Thépot, Leniency and Individual Liability: Opening the Black Box of the Cartel, Ssrn.com (2011), (Sept. 27, 2023, 09:15 AM) https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1932656

²¹ Florence Thépot, Leniency and individual liability, opening the 'black box' of the cartel, 7(2) COMPETITION LAW REVIEW 221, 222 (2011).

market power of the firm and not on the corporate governance policies regarding management/ownership structure of the firm which also has a role in the firm's anti-competitive behaviour.²²

Deciphering the Anti-Competitive behaviour, necessities interpreting it, in terms of economic notions like market power, competitive effects, entry, and efficiencies, and using the logical framework provided by economic theory to interpret the detailed facts involving a particular industry and specific challenged processes. The technique necessitates a thorough examination of the challenged behaviour's impact on competition, including identifying the market or markets in which competition has been hurt or is expected to be harmed, as well as the mechanism by which the challenged conduct does so.²³ Anti-competitive behaviours are driven by rapidly evolving businesses and technologies, keeping up with their pace and understanding the dynamics is complex²⁴. The inefficient rescue mechanism and strategies often result incompetent. Robust legal mechanism and integrating expert assistance to construe these challenges and solving these at the roots can be a real pull through.

IX. LANDMARK CASES IN THE INDIAN PHARMA INDUSTRY

A. Notable Legal Battles in the Indian Pharmaceutical Industry

The Competition Commission of India has addressed many instances of anti-competitive practices within the pharmaceutical sector's distribution chain. Through its investigations, the Commission has identified violations of section 3 of the Act committed by trade groups representing chemists and druggists. The case of *Varca Druggist & Chemist & Ors v. Chemists and Druggist Association, Goa* was the first case in which the Commission addressed matters pertaining to the pharmaceutical industry. Considering the enduring nature of established practises and their significant implications for public health, in addition to cases brought before the Commission as a result of filings, the Competition Commission of India (CCI) has also undertaken investigations of its own accord and has actively publicised the punitive measures taken against these local groups.

In the case of *Varca Druggist & Chemist & Others vs the Chemists & Druggists Association of Goa*²⁵ in 2012, a complaint was lodged by Varca Druggists. The complaint alleged that the Chemists & Druggists Association of Goa had been involved in engaging in restrictive trade practises. Following the repeal of the Monopolies and Restrictive Trade Practises Act, the matter was subsequently moved to the Competition Commission of India (CCI). The Commission has determined that the behaviour and policies of the Association have resulted in the restriction and regulation of drug supply in the Baroda district, as

²² Spencer Weber Waller, *Corporate Governance and Competition Policy*, 18 *Geo. Mason L. Rev.* 833 (2011).

²³ Jonathan B. Baker & Timothy F. Bresnahan, *Economic Evidence in Antitrust: Defining Markets and Measuring Market Power*, SSRN Electronic Journal (2006).

²⁴ Sanjana Srivastava & Arjun Gupta, *A Paradigmatic Analysis of Anti-Competitive Agreements and Cartelization - How India's Antitrust Watchdog Has Retaliated*, 4 *INDIAN J.L. & LEGAL Rsch.* 1 (2022).

²⁵ *Varca Druggist & Chemist & Others Vs Chemists & Druggists Association, Goa*, (2012) CompLR 838 (CCI).

per section 3(3)(b) of the Competition Act. The Association incurred a penalty imposed by the Competition Commission of India (CCI).

In the case of *M/s Arora Medical Hall, Ferozpur v. Chemists & Druggists Association, Ferozpur*²⁶ (CDAF), the CDAF imposed a compulsory requirement on prospective chemists/druggists seeking distributorship for pharmaceutical products from a company in Ferozpur. This requirement entailed obtaining a no objection certificate ("NOC") and a letter of credit (LOC) from the CDAF, accompanied by a payment of Rs. 2100/- per company. The individual in question was expelled from the core membership of the CDAF. Additionally, the CDAF organisation issued a request to its members, urging them to refrain from engaging in the procurement of items from the informant. The wholesalers were instructed to cease their transactions with the merchants who persisted in procuring merchandise from the informant. The aforementioned action contravened the stipulations outlined in both Section 3 and Section 4 of the legislation. During the investigation, the Director General discovered that the Compulsory Drug Approval Form mandated chemists and druggists to obtain an NOC from the CDAF. Additionally, it was observed that certain individuals were being denied NOCs, which consequently restricted their access to the market. As a result, the CDAF effectively regulated and limited the supply of drugs and medicines in Ferozpur. The implementation of the Competitive Displacement and Acquisition Framework (CDAF) resulted in the displacement of incumbent rivals from the market.

The Competition Commission of India determined that the actions of the CDAF are in violation of the provisions outlined in section 3(3)(b) in conjunction with section 3(1) of the Act since it imposes restrictions on the supply and provision of goods and services within the markets.

The Bengal Chemist and Druggist Association (BCDA) case is a suo moto case taken by the CCI for investigation. The BCDA represents a consortium comprising of pharmaceutical wholesalers and retailers. The entity was involved in actively or passively influencing the pricing of pharmaceuticals and exercising control over the distribution of medications in a coordinated fashion. Additionally, it issued anti-competitive communications instructing merchants to refrain from providing any discounts to customers. According to the findings of the Competition Commission of India (CCI), it was determined that the actions undertaken by the BCDA resulted in the restriction of trade, suppression of competition, and detriment to consumer welfare. The imposition of a penalty was a result of the violation of section 3(3) of the Act.²⁷

²⁶ Mrinali Mudoi, Recent Orders Of CCI Against Anti-Competitive Practices In The Pharmaceutical Industry, Mondaq (Sept. 28, 2023, 2:40 PM), <https://www.mondaq.com/india/antitrust-eu-competition-/321122/recent-orders-of-cci-against-anti-competitive-practices-in-the-pharmaceutical-industry>.

²⁷ *Bengal Chemist & Druggists Association V. Competition Commission of India*, 2017 SCC OnLine Cal 20337.

The case of *M/s Sandhya Drug Agency v. Assam Drug sellers Association & Ors.*²⁸ involved the submission of a complaint against several drug sellers associations on grounds of engaging in anti-competitive practises and exploiting their dominating market position. The cessation of drug delivery to the informant was a result of political divergences between the informant and the trade groups. The association of drug sellers was instructed to abstain from engaging in anti-competitive behaviours that contravened section 3 of the legislation. Furthermore, it was mandated that the cessation of practises such as the issuance of NOC appointment of stockists, the determination of trade margins, the collecting of product information service ("PIS") costs, and the boycott of pharmaceutical company products. The Competition Commission of India (CCI) levied a penalty for the contravention of Section 3 of the Act.

X. CONCLUSION

With India leading globally in the Pharmaceutical hub and being a dynamic industry by its very nature, the constant check on policies and their respective practices should be looked upon. To develop effective pharmaceutical industry, policymakers must have a prompt understanding of all the ways that acquisitions that can influence market power and increase costs. The governments should try to positively and strictly implement competition policies and regulations to avoid the anti-competitive practices originating from the underdevelopment of their legal systems and protectionist policies. To avoid cultural and social anti-competitive practices, proportionality is required with respect to the challenges, measures & aims; there must be minimal deterioration of the right to freedom along with restricted measures' consequences hand in hand with the legislative goal. Such practices should be reasonable and fair to international trade, are necessary to sustain the specific public policy objectives, and are the inevitable reflection of the particular situation unique to their countries. Further, from the economic lens, Competition Laws strict compliance must be ensured to ensure the consumer welfare, at large. This situation must be given due consideration by CCI, and it has a long way to go fulfilling its objectives.

²⁸ *Sandhya Drug Agency v. Assam Drug Dealers Associations*, Case No. 41/2011 (CCI).